

GENEOLOGICAL OR GENETIC CLASSIFICATION OF LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

Languages are grouped by diachronic relatedness into language families. In other words, languages are grouped based on how they were developed and evolved throughout history, with languages which descended from a common ancestor being grouped into the same language family.

Genetic classification sets the similarity of languages on the ground of their common ancestor. Typological classification sets the similarity of languages regardless from their affinity (relatedness), by common signs. Genetic classification.

By common ancestors languages divided into families, groups, subgroups and more little divisions. For example, Uzbek language – Turkic group – Uyghur subgroup – Altaic family. Russian language – Slavonic group – Eastern-Slavonic subgroup – Indo-European family – European branch. English language – Germanic group – Western-Germanic subgroup – Indo-European family. Languages that possess genetic ties with one another belong to the same linguistic grouping, known as a language family.

Introduction:

*Genealogical typology or Genetic classification sets the similarity of languages on the ground of their common ancestor. Typological classification on the other hand sets the similarity of languages regardless from their relatedness, by common signs. Languages that possess genetic ties with one another language belong to the same linguistic grouping, known as a language family. These ties are established through use of the comparative method of linguistic analysis, which relies mainly on shared phonological innovations as the test criteria. In linguistics, **genetic relationship** is the usual term for the relationship which exists between languages that are members of the same language family (Indo-European languages (Europe, Southwest to South Asia); Sino-Tibetan languages (East Asia); Niger-Congo languages (Sub-Saharan Africa); Afro-Asiatic languages (North Africa to Horn of Africa, Southwest Asia)). Two languages are considered to be genetically related if one is descended*

from the other or if both are descended from a common ancestor. For example, Italian is descended from Latin. Italian and Latin are therefore said to be genetically related. Spanish is also descended from Latin. Therefore, Spanish and Italian are genetically related.

Main part:

Genealogical typology is a branch of linguistic typology which studies the similarities and the relationship between the related languages. It is applied to the systems of genetically related languages. Genealogical typology developed from the comparative – historical linguistics dominated during the 19th century in Europe. Its origin was stimulated by the discovery of Sanskrit, the ancient classical language of India. The discovery of Sanskrit disclosed the possibility of a comparative study of languages. The concept of relative languages was confirmed by the existence in India of a sister of the familiar languages of Europe e.g. Sanskrit «mata» means «mother», in the accusative case «matarum»

Dvau-two

Trayah – three

As ti-he is etc.

Before the discovery of Sanskrit European linguistics possessed very vague similarities for the current grammars built on the Greek model. They didn't set clearly the features of each languages. It is worth to mention that at the same time Sanskrit discovery gave rise to confuse notions of linguistic relation which lived for a brief time that European languages were derived from Sanskrit. But this opinion gave way to a correct explanation, namely Sanskrit, Latin, Greek, and other were later forms of one prehistorically language.

Comparatives gave two kinds of classification of languages – genealogical and morphological.

Genealogical classification deals with the family relationship of languages which descend from one common ancestor. It distributes languages into different families.

Morphological classification deals with the classification of languages according to their structural features instead of a genealogical origin.

According to the morphological classification the languages are divided into:

Isolating (Chinese; Vietnamese; Japan; etc.)

Analytic (Russian; English; German; etc.)

Agglutinative (Turkish languages) and others.

Genetic Typology compares the systems of languages in two ways: diachronically and synchronically. But in the second case genetic relationship is not taken into consideration.

Conclusion:

Two languages are considered to be genetically related if one is descended from the other or if both are descended from a common ancestor. For example, Italian is descended from Latin. Italian and Latin are therefore said to be genetically related. Spanish is also descended from Latin. Therefore, Spanish and Italian are genetically related. Contact with another language can result in influence by it. For example, English has been influenced by French, Persian has been influenced by Arabic, and Japanese has been influenced by Chinese. However, this influence by definition does not constitute a genetic relationship.

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